

A new method for the determination of some organophosphate insecticides

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A quick and convenient method has been developed for milligram determination of some organophosphate insecticides. The sample is allowed to react with a calculated excess of (0.1 N) chloramine-T reagent in the presence of glacial acetic acid for 10–15 min at room temperature. After the reaction is over, KI solution (10%) is added and the unreacted reagent is back-titrated with 1 N solution of sodium thiosulfate to starch end-point. The method is applied for the determination of technical preparations of malathion (95%), dimethoate (90%), ethion (95%) and phorate (97%). The results are within the error of $\pm 1.0\%$.

Organophosphates are mainly used as insecticides. Procedures like liquid chromatographic¹, potentiometric², mass-spectrometric³, gas chromatographic⁴ and high performance liquid chromatographic⁵ are used for the determination of organophosphates. We report here a simple titrimetric method for the milligram determination of some organophosphate insecticides, e.g., malathion, dimethoate, ethion and phorate in technical form and in their formulations using chloramine-T reagent in acidic medium.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration, amount of the reagent and reaction temperature. Variation in reaction time was found to influence the speed of the reaction to an appreciable extent. In the determination of malathion, dimethoate and phorate in technical preparation and formulations, the results were obtained within 10 min while ethion required 15 min to complete the reaction. The percentage recovery of sample was fairly low at a lower reaction time due to incomplete reaction. It was established that the prescribed concentration of the reagent (0.1 N) was suitable for accurate results. A lower or higher concentration tends to give inaccurate results. Thus, to avoid the wastage of the reagent and to get accurate results, 0.1 N concentration of chloramine-T reagent was recommended for these estimation. The effect of volume of 0.1 N chloramine-T reagent was also studied in the estimation of organophosphates and it was observed that 5 ml of 0.1 N chloramine-T solution gives accurate results. The best recovery of the sample was obtained at room temperature (25–27°). Higher temperature gave inaccurate results because of decomposition of the reagents.

The results (Table 1) reveal that the proposed method can be used for the determination of organophosphate insecticides in technical preparations and formulations. The

values of standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV) and percentage error indicate that the proposed method is reproducible. Since the accuracy and precision of the method are good, the proposed method can easily be adopted.

The stoichiometry of the reagent with the sample depends on the structure of the compound. On the basis of stoichiometry and available literature, a possible course of reaction has been suggested for each compound. In case of malathion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S*-1, 2-dicarboethoxyethylthio-phosphate), it has been noted that 2 moles of chloramine-T are consumed under the prescribed reaction condition. This compound gets converted to the corresponding oxidized product,

In the series of organophosphate insecticide, dimethoate (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S-N*-methylcarbamoylmethylthio-phosphate) consumes 2 moles of chloramine-T and gets converted to the corresponding oxidized product,

Experimental

A 0.1 N chloramine-T (May & Baker) solution was prepared in distilled water and standardized iodometrically. A 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate (B.D.H.) solution in distilled water was prepared and standardized by titrating against primary standard copper sulfate solution iodometrically. A 0.1 N copper sulfate (G.R.) solution was prepared in distilled water containing small amount of dil. sulfuric acid to prevent hydrolysis of copper sulfate. A 10% aqueous solution of KI and a 2% aqueous solution of starch were prepared. Glacial acetic acid (Merck) was used without any dilution.

Stock solutions of the organophosphate insecticides (malathion, dimethoate, ethion and phorate) in technical forms and their formulations were made by dissolving accurately weighed amount of the sample (100 mg) in gl. acetic acid in 100- ml volumetric flask.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample (1–5 mg) were added 0.1 N chloramine-T solution (5 ml) and gl. acetic acid (5 ml). The flask containing the mixture was stoppered and the contents were allowed to react at room temperature (25–27°) for prescribed reaction time. Then 10% KI solution (5 ml) was added to it and titrated against standardized 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate solution to starch end-point. A blank experiment was also run.

Calculation : The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression :

$$\text{mg of the sample} = \frac{MN(B-S)}{n}$$

where, M is the molecular weight of the sample, N the normality of sodium thiosulfate solution, B the volume of sodium thiosulfate solution for blank, S the volume of sodium thiosulfate solution for the sample, n the number of mole of chloramine-T consumed per mole of the sample.

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